

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 6- Dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities

D6.2 NEON website and baseline communication material

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Abstract:	This document (D6.2) contains the set of NEON website and public communication materials. The first version of these materials has submitted on M6. Previously, in M3, the corporate identity with the NEON logo and the Brand Book were developed as part of the NEON project website included in this deliverable, and as described in the NEON Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1, M6).
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Executive summary

This deliverable (D6.1) contains NEON's website and the communication material design with a description of the challenges addressed by the project, its consortium, its objectives, and proposed solutions. It provides a description of the NEON's project website and its components and sections, it was made public in February 2022, meeting the deadline set in the Grant Agreement, but previous Beta versions were reviewed to start a permanent update process of its features that will maintain the website alive.

In terms of the Communication Materials, the deliverable contains the set of NEON public communication products design in form of graphical items. The first version of these materials is being submitted on M6. Previously, in M3, the corporate identity with the NEON logo was developed as part of the NEON project website, a description of which has been included in the NEON Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1, M6). Materials will be reassessed every six months to determine if contents need to be updated and redesigned and this deliverable will be updated accordingly with each reporting period. Considering the above, the communication materials included here are as follows: the project poster, the brochure, the project presentation, the newsletter template, and the initial set-up of the social media. The communication materials designed are included in this report and it details their description, with the corresponding screenshots.

On behalf of Authors

COMET Team

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1. Introduction

This document shows the implementation of the first version of the NEON website, which will be updated throughout the project with news, information, events, the status on the pilots' activities progress, and public deliverables produced by the project. It also details the process for requesting changes to the website, differentiating between bugs or errors, new content and new features or design changes. At the same time, the report presents some of the physical and virtual elements that will be used as part of our international communication and dissemination campaign to raise awareness of the NEON project. Through these means and others, the consortium plans to promote the concept and results of the NEON project to selected stakeholders and multipliers, such as the scientific community, technical experts, strategic experts and policy makers, stakeholders, the public and end-users.

Our overall stakeholder engagement strategy was described in the NEON Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1) in the following aspects: planned communication objectives, selected project messages, specific objectives, stakeholders, methodology and instruments, timetable, and work plan and finally, the monitoring of the communication and dissemination plan.

The materials created and presented in this deliverable come to support these objectives, materially and visually, constituting a significant and ongoing step of the project communication, after the creation of the corporate visual identity for the project website. This deliverable, with the corresponding communication materials, is part of Task 6.2 (Dissemination and communication strategy) of WP6, whose main objective is the promotion and wide dissemination of the project, also wanting to support the rest of the work packages and the long-term objectives of the NEON project.

2. Website Development Background

2.1. Context

The first version of the NEON website contains the fundamental visual and written information for visitors to learn more about the project's scope, objective, pilot sites, and enabling technologies. It also puts in place the first functionalities to allow visitors to engage with the project: a simple subscription form to the project's newsletters and a contact form for interested stakeholders to be able to reach out to the project.

The development of both the concept and image of the website are in line with the creation of NEON's corporate identity, as described in Section VISUAL IDENTITY, and aim to present the project's key concepts and values to the public in a more extended way. More specifically, the website's graphic design and images aim to emphasise the technological and innovative character of the project while remaining modern, minimalist, and friendly. These visual concepts are paired with written contents that explain in a detailed but approachable manner the main concepts and the different levels that constitute NEON's technological development.

In this sense, the website has been designed to maintain a challenging, attractive, and playful relationship with the user.

The website will be periodically updated according to the project's results and the development of other activities which will allow us to have a clearer view of NEON stakeholders and the exploitation approach.

2.2. General Data Protection Regulation

The European Union's ('EU') General Data Protection Regulation ('GDPR') is the current European legislation that controls and manages the processing by an individual, a company or an organization of personal data relating to individuals within the EU. The entry into force of this regulation was on 25 May 2018 and thus NEON website should comply with it to guarantee data protection and privacy.

For this reason, the consortium has implemented the "Privacy Policy" and "Terms and Conditions" sections, which are always accessible to interested users. Access via links to this section is located visibly in the website footer of the "Home Page". It should be noted that the only point of entry of personal information through the website are the contact form and the subscription to newsletter, following the new EU regulation. For the case of subscription to the newsletter, the specific acceptance of the privacy policy is required to be done, by checking the corresponding box on the website and by verifying the email account through an automatic process.

2.3. Next steps

Immediate next steps will be:

2.3.1. Implementing new content based on the information coming from the results of the other Work

Packages and the feedback gathered from partners. As a more immediate example we would like to:

- Linking the website to the project's social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn) once created (M6).
- Enrich the "Pilot Sites" section with new contents testimonials and feedback from the workshops and e-seminars (M7–M30).
- Expand the information on the associated technology identified during the project, on the "Technology enablers" section and/or, once the pertinent content becomes available, by adding it to the Publications & Results section.

2.3.2. Build upon the "News & Media" section

Publishing regular news, events, articles, and content of relevance to stakeholders, the public and the press to maximise impact and act according to the strategy and key messages defined in the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of results (M6).

2.3.3. Complementing and inciting web traffic

Through actions on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn).

2.3.4. Gathering feedback from partners

Through the process defined in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** of the present document.

2.4. Section and Contents

2.4.1. Content Management System

NEON’s website uses WordPress as CMS (Content Management System), which is by far the most popular CMS at present: used by approximately 75 million websites. WordPress is Open Source, free to install, deploy, and upgrade. It is also supported by a large community of users and developers, which facilitates the maintenance of sites in terms of problem solving, thereby reducing development costs and implementation time.

Moreover, WordPress, as a flexible and simple interface to publish and curate content, will allow the collaboration of any project partner or any other stakeholder to publish content in our website. There are thousands of WordPress plugins and interface templates. Regarding the plugins, a fully GDPR compliance to manage newsletters and another one to manage downloads were installed.

2.4.2. Home Page

The project’s landing page is the backbone of the website as it is presenting the project and its most characteristic features and objectives in a visual and straightforward approach, inviting users to interact with its different contents in order to learn more about the particularities and highlights of the project. In the image below you can see a screenshot of the full homepage design.

Sections **Figure 1. NEON Website home page**

The sections of the first version of NEON’s website are briefly describe hereinafter. It should be noticed that the sections could be changed in the future, according to the project’s needs. Currently the main sections, present both in the Home Page display and in the Menu bar, are the following:

- Project
- Enabling Technologies
- Partners
- Pilots and Adopters
- News
- Publications & Results
- Contact

The general structure underlying the website would correspond to that of the sitemap attached in the figure below.

Figure 2. NEON Site Map with the different sections defined

2.4.3. Project Section

The “Project Section” is the main section of the website and, as such, corresponds to the homepage. It aims to present a comprehensive description of the project within the European context of the coordination and support action and funding, sets out the main characteristics of NEON, the challenge it meets, the problems it intends to solve, the solutions proposed, and other tips, in the learn more sub section.

To present this information in a simple and understandable way, the contents have been grouped under four sub-sections, which are directly accessible via the main menu, as follows:

The **NEON Approach** and what the project is: this section presents short description of the project so users can quickly understand what the project is about. It is also included the concepts based on effective energy services that NEON aims to develop.

Figure 3. NEON Approach subsection

The Challenges: this section aims to summarise the five challenges proposed to be faced in the proposed in the project.

The Objectives: this section introduces the six objectives to face the challenges mentioned in the subsection above.

Learn More: includes direct links to other four sections of the project can be found.

2.4.3. Enabling Technologies Section

This section explains the 10 key enabling technologies for the integrated energy services and business models. Each enabling technology has its own description box, it can also be improved by creating independent pages to each enabling technology according to the project progress and results obtained.

Figure 4. NEON Enabling Technologies Section

2.4.4. Pilot Sites Section

This section includes the description of the four citizen energy communities (CECs), that will serve as early adopters. Each pilot site has its own box that will be improved with images and other information including and independent page to each site.

Figure 5. NEON Pilot Sites Section in website

2.4.5. The Partners Section

This section is dedicated to presenting the members of the Consortium, both visually and textually, including links to the websites and social networks of the different institutions and companies. The page includes descriptions, logos and links to the different companies and institutions that make up NEON.

Figure 6. NEON Partners section in website

2.4.6. News and Events Section

This section is dedicated to News, Events, Press Releases and Articles so interested stakeholders may keep up to date with the project’s evolution, progress, and results.

2.4.7. Publication and Results Section

All the project’s public files will be placed in this section. It will also include scientific publications and the results generated in the project.

Figure 7. NEON Publications and Results section in website

2.4.8. Contact us

This section is a simple form that allows interested stakeholders to contact the project. The form acts as an email-equivalent so users may send us questions, comments, or suggestions. It is connected to the project's e-mail account managed by COMET to be able to reply to interested parties.

3. Website Change and Update Process

It is expected that the NEON website will change according to the project development, these changes may refer to design, content, new functionalities, or changes in the CMS (Content Management System) code, among others.

Website changes should be properly reported, discussed, budgeted, and planned. It should be noticed that the budget and effort for the website is limited and the needs and subjective impressions from the consortium partners may differ in aspects like the design or the communication style.

The following process is proposed to properly address changes for the website:

Figure 8. Flowchart of the web change management process

1. Partner X considers/realizes about the need to make a change to the website.
2. Partner X should classify this change as an error/bug (2.1) or changes regarding content/feature – including design changes (2.2).
 - 2.1. Errors and bugs should be reported by using the most effective method available and will be solved by the communication team as soon as possible.
 - 2.2. For changes regarding content or features, it is mandatory to fill the form.
 - 2.2.1. The Communication team will evaluate the change request. Effort, cost and usability –heuristic evaluation– will be evaluated. In this way, the requested change can be prioritized.
 - 2.2.1.1. If everything is clear for the communication team, the change will be planned.
 - 2.2.1.2. If not, the change should be discussed.

2.2.1.2.1. The change is approved and planned after the discussion.

2.2.1.2.2. The change is rejected.

A website change form will be used to trace the changes done during the webpage lifecycle.

4. Visual Identity

NEON’s visual identity is inspired by the project’s aim of unifying the new concepts that will create the next-generation integrated energy services for communities. The logo is constructed with the letters forming the word “*neon*” with a circle on the top of each character, creating the visual effect of people together. The word neon is the acronym of the project but is also gives the idea of electrical light with the neon gas inside the old incandescent bulbs.

With a minimalist approximation, NEON’s logo seeks to attribute the brand with characteristics that can be recognized as modern accessible, inclusive, friendly, neutral, and dynamic.

4.1. Logo

Figure 9. NEON Project Logo in different colour options, corporate colours, black and white, and grey

4.2. Colour Pallet

The corporate colour palette works mainly with washed shades of black, green, and blue. This range of colours allows designing graphics and artworks that are visually attractive and contrasting.

This primary gamut approach seeks to widely engage with users and offer enough variables to illustrate the project’s concepts on the sustainable innovations of NEON energy communities’ concept.

<p>BLACK:</p> <p>#0F1E29</p> <p>R15 G30 B41</p>	<p>GREEN:</p> <p>#4FB8A7</p> <p>R79 G184 B167</p>
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<p>BLUE:</p> <p>#43A1DA</p> <p>R67 G161 B218</p>	<p>NEON GRADIENT:</p>
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NEON IDENTITY / CORPORATE COLORS

COLORS LOGO CONSTRUCTION:

SECONDARY COLOR:

NEON
GRADIENT

#0F1E29
R15 G30 B41

#43A1DA
R67 G161 B218

#4FB8A7
R79 G184 B167

Figure 10. NEON Corporate colours pallet

4.3. Typographic Fonts

The logo has been built with the open-source font Stick No Bills Semi Bold. For all corporate communications, the Urbanist Regular family is the recommended font.

NEON IDENTITY /
CORPORATE TYPOGRAPHY

FONTS FOR LOGO CONSTRUCTION:

Stick No Bills SemiBold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOpPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234569\$%&/()=?;! "# : ; - @

RECOMMENDED FONT FOR TEXTS:

Urbanist Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOpPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234569\$%&/()=?;! "# : ; - @

Figure 11. NEON Typographic fonts

5. PUBLIC COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

The NEON project's public communication kit includes materials that have already been developed and made available to the public (such as the project's corporate identity, logo and website), materials that have recently been prepared (included in this deliverable) and materials that will be developed in the future. All materials developed for the duration of the project will be part of this deliverable.

This first batch of materials presented in M6 consist of the first versions of the poster and roll-up, the brochure, the project presentation, the triptych, the newsletter template, and the set-up for social media. Materials will be reviewed and reassessed every six months to establish if contents need to be updated and redesigned o fit the projects evolutions and results. Updates to this deliverable will include new versions of the materials and will be submitted every reporting period.

All these materials ultimately are a graphic and explanatory extension of the project, diversified into different types of documents depending on the function and the target audience, which will contribute to disseminating the project through different channels, such as the web, social networks, public presentations, etc.

The attached communication package aims to provide partners, public, stakeholders, and journalists with different materials that explain and illustrate the following: challenges faced by the project, opportunities it takes, proposals it offers, and finally, main concepts, objectives, methods, technologies and demonstration sites.

5.1. Posters

A roll-up poster has been designed as an important tool for general project visibility during events, conferences, open days, and workshops. The poster has been designed with an informative, but also explanatory and pedagogical intention, so in addition to informing, it explains some technical aspects of the project. The roll-up includes key project information as title, main concepts, consortium partners, project impacts, pilot sites and technologies used.

An A1 poster was created early on with the objective of providing partners with an easy-to-print version, as it can be easily readjusted to A3 format. This poster includes key project information, pilot sites and technologies, partners, website, and social media.

Figure 12. NEON Roll-up Poster

Figure 13. NEON A1 Poster

5.2. Brochure and Triptych

An initial 16-page brochure has been created to inform on the project details and to provide information on the project consortium, as well as reference links and contact information.

The aim of the brochure is to clarify to the readers the different aspects of the project (challenges, opportunities, objectives, technologies, pilot sites, consortium members, etc.), as well as to motivate their engagement, to get the readers to subscribe to the newsletter and visit the website and social networks so that they are informed and committed to the project throughout its life.

This brochure can be adapted for each NEON partner, depending on the event or workshop, to fit specific needs upon request. A summary triptych has also produced to be delivered as alternative and easy communication material.

Figure 14. NEON Brochure

Figure 15. NEON Triptych

5.3. Social Media

NEON will be communicating on Twitter and LinkedIn, promoting the project, disseminating its progress, and generating a progressively growing network of members and followers. In both social media we are sharing news, updates, events in which we participate, and other contents of interest. The activity carried out in social networks is being monitored to ensure that it follows the progress established in the KPIs defined in the NEON Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1).

5.3.1. Twitter

The Twitter account will be published in March 2022. As the project advances, we will link it, among other users, to the European Commission and its different agencies and organizations, to the H2020 ongoing and Horizon Europe's sister projects, as well as numerous stakeholders, public authorities, investors, and potential users.

5.3.2. LinkedIn

The LinkedIn page is targeted to professionals, stakeholders, potential users, public authorities, and investors. As we develop this network, it will become a member of related H2020 ongoing projects and Horizon Europe featured groups. The LinkedIn account will be also published in March 2022.

5.4. Project Presentation Templates

A PowerPoint standard presentation has been created for the NEON partners to be displayed when presenting the project at conferences, meetings, fairs, and other events. The 20-slide presentation is a baseline guide that provides key project information. It can be adapted or completed by each partner for specific needs or events. It will be updated through the lifespan of the project to reflect as needed the project results and newer contents.

5.5. Newsletter

With the aim of reaching out to our stakeholders and public, regular newsletters will be issued with a summary of the project's news, articles, activities, and highlights. The newsletter has been designed as an interactive PDF to allow partners to easily share via email and for easy download via the NEON Website. It will also be promoted and linked to via NEON's social media platforms. The first newsletter will be sent at the end of year 1 of the project.

Figure 16. NEON Newsletter Template

6. Conclusion

The production and update of the NEON Project Website and the Communication Materials are ongoing and the project long activity that complements and builds upon those steps are taken with the creation of the corporate visual identity of the project and the launch of the website. They are important tools that provide partners, stakeholders, journalists, followers of the project and the general public, a fundamental knowledge of the NEON project. Through a set of different communication materials that will be developed during the project life (Rollup, brochure, posters, newsletter, video, PowerPoint presentation, etc.), NEON social, climatic, economic, energy and technological context has been introduced, as well as the challenges the project faces, the proposals and solutions it offers, the technologies and innovations on which it relies, its different demonstration sites, and its different channels and contact points to encourage further engagement and follow-up with the project throughout its whole life.

In the next elaboration of communication materials stage, a further step will be taken, through the creation of the further digital and/or printed materials, the generation of project content for social media and the launching of project video content. All of them are more complex and elaborated communication materials that will help to deepen the understanding of the project and its progress, and to continue encouraging active involvement with the project.

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